

Maternal serum lipidomic identifies lysophosphatidic acid as a predictor of small for gestational age neonates

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Abstract

To discover lipidomic alterations during pregnancy in mothers who subsequently delivered small for gestational age (SGA) neonates and identify predictive lipid markers that can help recognize and manage these mothers, we carried out untargeted lipidomics on maternal serum samples collected between 24-28 weeks of gestation. We used a nested case-control study design and serum from mothers who delivered SGA and appropriate for gestational age babies. We applied untargeted lipidomics using mass spectrometry to characterize lipids and discover changes associated with SGA births during pregnancy. Multivariate pattern recognition software Collaborative Laboratory Integrated Reports (CLIR) was used for the post-analytical recognition of range differences in lipid ratios that could differentiate between SGA and control mothers and their integration for complete separation between the two groups. Here, we report changes in lipids from serum collected during pregnancy in mothers who delivered SGA neonates. In contrast to normal pregnancies where lysophosphatidic acid increased over the course of the pregnancy owing to increased activity of lysophospholipase D, we observed a decrease (32%; $P=.05$) of 20:4-lysophosphatidic acid in SGA mothers, which could potentially compromise fetal growth and development. Integration of lipid ratios in an interpretive tool (CLIR) could completely separate SGA mothers from controls demonstrating the power of untargeted lipidomic analyses for identifying novel predictive biomarkers. Additional studies are required for further assessment of the lipid biomarkers identified in this report.

Keywords

Mass spectrometry; biomarkers; pregnancy; lysophosphatidic acid; triglyceride

Introduction

Intrauterine growth restriction is defined as failure of the fetus to achieve its optimal growth potential.¹ Small for gestational age (SGA) fetuses or newborns are those smaller in size than normal for their gestational age, most commonly defined as a weight below the 10th percentile for the sex-specific gestational age.² SGA pregnancy is a major clinical and public health problem, mainly in low and middle income countries. In 2012, an estimated 23 million neonates were born with SGA in low- and middle-income countries with South Asia bearing the largest burden³. SGA pregnancy is an important risk factor for stillbirth and deaths in the neonatal and post-neonatal periods. Small size at birth either due to preterm birth or SGA pregnancy accounts for more than 80% of neonatal deaths and increases risk of post-neonatal mortality, growth failure, and adult-onset non-communicable diseases including type 2 diabetes, coronary heart disease and hypertension.^{4,5} The increased risk of mortality and morbidity associated with SGA can be averted substantially through early identification of mothers at risk of delivering SGA babies prenatally and proper management. However, there are no viable biomarkers available for predicting SGA birth during pregnancy.

Lipids are major constituents of membrane in cellular systems and play multiple cellular functions in signaling and energy storage.⁶ Altered metabolism of lipids has been reported in numerous diseases including cancer, cardiovascular diseases and other diseases, proving significance of lipids as biomarkers.^{7,8,9,10} Structural determination of lipids can be achieved by mass spectrometry (MS). Advances in MS and lipidomics software tools have advanced identification and

quantitation of lipids in parallel.¹¹ Separation of lipids by liquid chromatography (LC) prior to MS, reduces ion suppression and yields a higher number of identified lipids.¹²

Studies have indicated an association of dysregulated lipoproteins to complicated pregnancies as triglyceride-rich lipoproteins and small, dense low-density lipoproteins are elevated in preeclampsia¹³ and changes in lipids, lipoproteins and apolipoproteins have been reported in mothers who delivered SGA neonates.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ SGA neonates also have been reported to show altered lipid profiles including decreased fatty acid and high triglyceride levels.^{17,18,19} However, most studies have focused on analysis only at birth with only limited reports on maternal serum prior to birth. One study reported elevation of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) at 24-26 weeks of gestation in mothers who subsequently delivered SGA neonates.²⁰ As the degree of elevation was relatively small (~5%) and HDL is known to be increased during normal pregnancies with a decline at term, it is challenging to predict SGA births based on HDL levels. Nevertheless, such findings raise the possibility that other lipidomic alterations could also occur during pregnancy. Indeed, a recent study has reported higher levels of plasma glycerophospholipids and sphingolipids and decreased urinary metabolites from SGA mothers at 20 weeks of gestation,²¹ which again indicates that lipidomic changes are highly likely to precede SGA births.

In this study, we sought to investigate if lipidomic alterations could be detected in pregnant mothers who subsequently delivered SGA neonates (weight for gestational age <3rd percentile).²² Because 24-28 weeks of gestation is early in terms of fetal growth (the fetus weighs 765-1,618 grams during this period²²), the fetus is highly vulnerable to metabolic alterations in the mother. To identify predictive lipid markers that can help identify mothers who subsequently delivered

small for gestational age (SGA) neonates for a more effective clinical management, we carried out untargeted lipidomics on maternal serum samples of Bangladeshi women collected between 24-28 weeks of gestation.

Materials and Methods

Study design

The Alliance for Maternal and Newborn Health Improvement (AMANHI) – Bangladesh established a biorepository in a cohort of pregnant women and their newborns in Bangladesh.²³ Between 2014 and 2018, the project prospectively enrolled pregnant women identified through population-based surveillance. Briefly, trained community health workers identified pregnant women through 2 monthly home visits and obtained informed consent to participate in the study. All pregnancies were confirmed via a strip-based pregnancy test at home administered by Community health workers and gestational age was determined using ultrasound before 20 weeks of gestation in the study clinic. Epidemiological and phenotype data from the pregnant women were collected during antenatal and post-natal visits. The study protocol was approved by the ethics committees of the International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh, the John Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, and the World Health Organization.

Sample processing, storage and study design

Maternal blood samples were collected between 24-28 weeks of gestation and stored in plasma

and serum aliquots at -80°C . SGA cases were women who spontaneously delivered live born, singleton babies with no known congenital malformations and a weight for gestational age of $<3^{\text{rd}}$ percentile according to Intergrowth reference.²⁴ Controls were women who also delivered live born, singleton babies under the aforementioned criteria except for a weight for gestational age of $\geq 50^{\text{th}}$ percentile.²² There were 511 SGA cases and 254 controls in AMANHI biorepository and we used serum samples from 20 mothers who delivered SGA babies and 20 control mothers. Gestational age was determined by ultrasound scans conducted between 8-19 weeks of gestation.

Lipid extraction

A modified Bligh and Dyer method was utilized to extract lipids from 50 μl serum.²⁵ A mixture of internal standards (lysophosphatidic acid (LM1701), lysophosphatidylcholine (LM1601), lysophosphatidylethanolamine (856707), lysophosphatidylglycerol (858127), phosphatidic acid (830856), phosphatidylcholine (850360), phosphatidylethanolamine (830756), lysophosphatidylglycerol (830456), phosphatidylinositol (LM1502), lysosphingomyelin (860656), ceramide (860517), glucosylceramide (860569), sphingomyelin (860585), diglyceride (330722), triglyceride (860903) and cholesteryl ester (700186) from Avanti Polar Lipids, AL) equivalent to 75 pmol was added to all samples equally prior to the extraction, followed by addition of 1 ml of extraction solvent, consisted of chloroform:methanol (1:2, v/v). All samples were incubated on ice for 10 min and centrifuged at $13,800\times g$ for 2 min at 4°C . A single phase of organic solvent was observed along with a protein precipitate, which appeared as a pellet at the bottom of the tube. To avoid disturbing the protein pellet, 950 μl of supernatant was collected and to remaining protein pellet, 750 μl of chloroform:methanol:37% 1M HCl (40:80:1, v/v/v) was added, vortexed and left

at room temperature for 15 min. 250 μ l of ice-cold chloroform was added, followed by addition of 450 μ l of 0.1M HCl, to create two phase separation. Samples were centrifuged at 6,500 \times g for 2 min at 4°C and the bottom organic layer was collected, combined with previously collected organic layer and vacuum dried. The dried lipid extracts were kept at -80°C until liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analysis.

Lipid profiling using high performance liquid chromatography- tandem mass spectrometry

Q Exactive Plus Hybrid Quadrupole Orbitrap mass spectrometer was coupled to an Ultimate 3000 RSLCnano UHPLC (both from Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA) for untargeted lipidomics. Accucore C₁₈ (2.6 μ m, 2.1 \times 150 mm, Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA) was used as a column at 60°C. With a flow rate of 250 μ l/min, extracted lipids equivalent to 2 μ l of serum and 5 pmol of internal standard mixture was injected using mobile phase A (H₂O:acetonitrile = 9:1, v/v) and lipids were eluted according to the degree of hydrophobicity under the binary gradient with the mobile phase B (isopropanol:methanol:acetonitrile = 7:2:1, v/v/v) for 30 min. Both mobile phases contained 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid as modifiers. Analysis was carried out in a data-dependent mode using higher collision dissociation technique by alternating between positive and negative ion modes throughout the run. Stepped collision energy of 30 and 35 eV in negative ion mode while 20 and 30 eV were used in the positive ion mode. All samples were analyzed blinded in a randomized order throughout the data acquisition and data was acquired by alternating between positive and negative ion modes.

Data processing and statistical analysis

Continuous variables in the descriptive demographic and clinical characteristics of neonates in the AMANHI-Bangladesh biorepository and mothers used in the study are reported as mean with standard deviation and median with interquartile range while categorical variables are expressed as absolute frequency count and percentages (Table 1).

LipidSearch 4.0 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA), a web-based tool for lipid identification, was utilized to identify lipids based on precursor mass and corresponding product ions from MS/MS spectra. The quantitation of identified lipids was achieved by calculating the peak area of each lipid using PyQuant and Xcalibur, in reference of that of internal lipid for normalization.²⁶ We calculated average fold-change of lipids between SGA and control mothers. Statistical comparison of lipid profiles between the groups was carried out using two-tailed Student's t-test with unequal variance. Statistical analysis was performed using R version 4.0 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing). Any lipid with $P \leq 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

Collaborative Laboratory Integrated Reports (CLIR; <https://clir.mayo.edu>) was used as a post-analytical integrative tool to quantitative results of lipidomics, in order to find ratios of lipids that can differentiate cases from controls.²⁷ Quantitative values from all 496 lipids analyzed in the study were included in this analysis. Educational material describing the principle of a min max score and the creation and use of this tool is available on-line, (<https://news.mayocliniclabs.com/2013/06/18/new-hot-topic-the-region-4-stork-r4s-collaborative-project-part-3-post-analytical-interpretive-tools/>).

Results

Untargeted profiling of lipids

Demographic and clinical characteristics of SGA (n=20) and control (n=20) mothers used in the study are listed in Table 1. Mothers across the groups had no significant differences in their characteristics. All SGA and controls mothers had similar mean and median age and gestational age at blood draw and delivery, hemoglobin level and blood pressure.

We analyzed species from 16 subclasses of lipids from extracted serum lipids, where zwitterionic phospholipids (lysophosphatidylcholine and phosphatidylcholine), sphingolipids (ceramide, monohexosylceramide, dihexosylceramide, trihexosylceramide, sphingomyelin and monosialodihexosylganglioside), sterol lipids (cholesteryl ester) and glycerides (diglyceride and triglyceride (TG)) were analyzed in the positive ion mode while anionic phospholipids (lysophosphatidylethanolamine, phosphatidylethanolamine, lysophosphatidic acid (LPA), lysophosphatidylinositol and phosphatidylinositol) were analyzed in the negative ion mode. A total of 496 serum lipids were structurally identified based on their MS/MS spectra using the methodology described above. As an example, Fig. 2A depicts MS/MS spectra of 38:4-phosphatidylinositol isomers (m/z 885.55). Fragment ion at m/z 241.01 is a signature ion of the polar head group of phosphatidylinositol while other fragments at m/z 78.96 (PO_3^-) and 96.97 (H_2PO_4^-) are dissociated from m/z 241.01. Additional fragment ions at m/z 225.23 and 331.26 on the left panel reflect the deprotonated fatty acyl chains of 16:0 and 22:4, respectively, while those at m/z 283.26 and 303.23 on the right panel represent fatty acyl chains of 18:0 and 20:4. Unlike

other classes of lipids where isomeric lipids were separated due to the difference in fatty acyl chains, isomeric TG could not be separated due to their structural reasons; TG exist in different combinations in 3 fatty acyl chains, which allow a single fatty acyl chain to often be present in more than one isomeric forms of TG (Fig. 2B) making their retention times overlap closely and elute as one peak. Therefore, unable to separate and distinguish isomeric TG species at both MS and MS/MS level, all TG lipids identified in the study are listed in ‘total number of carbons in fatty acyl chains:total number of double bonds in fatty acyl chains’, such as 52:3-TG. Supplementary Table S1 list a number of subclasses of lipids identified from the present study.

Alterations of lipids in SGA mothers during 24-28 weeks of gestation

Of the serum lipids that we annotated and quantified, several subspecies from various classes of lipids showed pronounced changes in SGA mothers during 24-28 weeks of gestation. This included LPA species that were decreased while most of the triglyceride (TG) species were generally increased in SGA mothers (Fig. 3A and 3B). One of the LPA subspecies, 20 carbons with 4 double bonds in fatty acyl chain (20:4-LPA), showed pronounced changes ($P=.05$) in SGA mothers during 24-28 weeks of gestation (Fig. 4A). Other subspecies of LPA and TG that were altered in SGA mothers are shown in Fig. 4A and 4B, respectively.

CLIR is a multivariate pattern recognition software developed and maintained by Mayo Clinic.²⁷ As a tool that was originally developed for the post-analytical interpretation of expanded newborn screening by tandem mass spectrometry, its application can extend to find biomarkers and support diagnostics of other diseases. CLIR is proven to improve clinical performance and near-zero false

positive rates.²⁸⁻³⁰ Instead of relying solely on measured lipid species, CLIR automatically calculated all possible permutation of ratios (~57,000) of which 491 ratios exhibited $\leq 50\%$ overlap between the ranges of controls and SGA. Of these, we retained the 10 best lipid ratios that can segregate SGA cases from controls (Table 2). These most informative ratios for SGA were then integrated into a single condition tool for each condition that produced a score and a percentile rank, an objective measure of likelihood of disease. These two parameters were then merged into a dual scatter plot, which can be used for differential diagnosis. This tool demonstrates that a combination of 10 informative lipid ratios can segregate SGA mothers from controls (Fig. 3C).²⁷

These lipid ratios consisted of different combinations of 15 lipids species from various classes of lipids. Notably, five out of the 10 ratios included 20:4-LPA as the denominator (Table 2). Therefore, we examined changes in the total LPA and its various subspecies in greater detail. Of the various LPA species whose fatty acyl chains were confirmed, 20:4-LPA species was the most abundant lipid molecule (constituting ~45% of total LPA) as its MS signal was the highest in both control and SGA mothers and it was decreased significantly in SGA mothers by 32% ($P=.05$; Fig.5A). Although not statistically significant, the total LPA also showed a decreasing trend in SGA mothers (33%; $P=.08$) while several other subspecies of LPA were also decreased; 18:2-LPA by 44% ($P=.18$), 18:0-LPA by 37% ($P=.18$) and 16:0-LPA by 32% ($P=.24$). Overall, LPA levels along with changes in individual LPA species (containing stearic, palmitic, oleic, linoleic or arachidonic acid) in SGA mothers are illustrated in Fig. 5A that show a 32-44% decrease.

Discussion

Lysophosphatidic acids are decreased in SGA mothers

It is noteworthy that the bioactive molecule LPA was decreased in SGA mothers during gestation. LPA can be synthesized from hydrolysis of lysophospholipids to LPA by lysophospholipase D, which is identical to autotaxin and *ENPP2*.^{31,32} Synthesis of LPA by lysophospholipase D is known to occur from various sources including lipoproteins, exosomes and dietary intake.³³ LPA activates signaling through G protein-coupled receptors and affects multiple mediators including Ras, Rho, Akt, MAPK and PKC mediated downstream signaling pathways.³⁴ Activation of these mediators subsequently influences multiple cellular processes including apoptosis, differentiation and migration and developmental processes involving blood vessels, immune cells, bones and cerebral cortex.³⁴ LPA is also known to induce growth and development of embryos as it plays critical roles in embryo spacing and implantation.³⁵ Six LPA receptor genes have been identified, *LPAR1-6*, and null mutations of individual or multiple genes in this subfamily lead to developmental defects including restricted growth in size and embryonic lethality.³⁶⁻³⁸ As activity of lysophospholipase D increases nearly 5-fold over the course of a normal pregnancy, LPA exhibits a concomitant increase with the progression of normal gestation.³¹ In contrast to normal pregnancy, we observed a decrease in LPA, which likely results from decreased activity of lysophospholipase D. The abnormal decrease in LPA levels may contribute to growth restriction and small stature of SGA neonates. Further, because LPA with arachidonic acid (20:4-LPA) exhibited marked decrease in SGA mothers, defects in neurocognitive abilities and underdevelopment of brain in children born as SGA neonates^{39,40} could result from the requirement of arachidonic acid as one of essential fatty acids for development and normal functioning of the central nervous system.⁴¹ A decrease in LPA levels can lead to short stature, restriction in growth and insufficient placental development, all

leading to SGA neonates (Fig. 5B).

Triglycerides (TG) are increased in SGA mothers

Many studies have documented increased level of total TG in cord blood of SGA neonates immediately after delivery,^{14, 16, 42, 43} and in maternal serum before delivery.¹⁴ In line with these results, we discovered increased levels of TG during 24-28 weeks of gestation in SGA pregnancy (Fig. 3B). Elevation of TG during pregnancy is considered as a normal physiological change brought about by increased insulin resistance and estrogen, especially during late pregnancy (24-32 weeks).⁴⁴ Elevated circulating TG and their remnants are prone for increased lipid peroxidation progressively producing free radicals and lipid peroxides. This enhances the oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and possibly insulin resistance. Membrane-bound low-density lipoprotein receptor related protein-1 increases intracellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate levels, increasing the protein kinase A activity. This inhibits migration of TG rich lipoproteins to vascular smooth muscle cells, which is essential for protection against vascular diseases.⁴⁵ Hentschke et.al reported decreased expression of low-density lipoprotein receptor related protein-1 in placentas of mothers who delivered SGA babies.⁴⁵ This in addition to lipid peroxides has the potential to damage the endothelial cells in the placenta. This may lead to disruption in development of normal placental villi causing impaired secretion of pro-angiogenic placenta growth factor.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ Placental insufficiency, followed by chronic hypoxic state will be resulted in the developing fetus, which is one of the factors for intrauterine growth restriction in SGA babies (Fig. 4B).⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸

Limitation of the study

A possible limitation of the study is the differences in body mass index (BMI) of case and control mothers. In the study population, 40.5% of mothers with SGA were underweight and 2.1% were overweight. In contrast, the underweight and overweight rates were 29.1% and 9.1%, respectively, among control mothers. Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI is known to be associated with weight for gestational age of the babies. For this study, we randomly selected SGA cases with weight for gestational age <3rd percentile and controls with weight for gestational age >50th percentile. Since we did not obtain strict BMI-matched controls, the distribution of BMI in the study sample was more extreme than the underlying population. Because our interest is to identify markers of SGA, we believe that this difference may not introduce any significant bias. However, to address any potential of bias, we will select validation cohorts based on matched BMI in our future studies.

Conclusions

Our results highlight that lipid ratios can be used to predict SGA neonates during pregnancy and that LPA is a potential predictive biomarker for SGA. If validated in a larger cohort, these findings are significant both from an early diagnosis standpoint as well as for early therapeutic intervention of at-risk mothers to help prevent SGA newborns.

Author contributions

Seul Kee Byeon: Conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, data curation, investigation, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; **Rasheda Khanam:** conceptualization, investigation, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; **Sayedur Rahman:** supervision of field work, investigation, writing – review & editing;; **Tarik Hasan:** biospecimen collection and processing, investigation, writing – review & editing;; **Syed Jafar Raza Rizvi:** data curation, writing – review & editing; **Anil K. Madugundu:** formal analysis; **Madan Gopal Ramarajan:** writing – review & editing; **Jae Hun Jung:** formal analysis; **Nabidul H Chowdhury:** data curation, writing – review & editing; **Salahuddin Ahmed:** project administration, writing – review & editing; **Rubhana Raqib:** writing- review and editing; **Kwang Pyo Kim:** writing – review & editing; **Amy L. Piazza:** software, **Piero Rinaldo:** software, writing – review & editing, **Akhilesh Pandey:** Conceptualization, supervision, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; **Abdullah Baqui:** Conceptualization, supervision, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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References

1. A. Lausman, J. Kingdom and C. Maternal Fetal Medicine, *J Obstet Gynaecol Can*, 2013, **35**, 741-748.
2. E. P. Schlaudecker, F. M. Munoz, A. Bardaji, N. S. Boghossian, A. Khalil, H. Mousa, M. Nesin, M. I. Nisar, V. Pool, H. M. L. Spiegel, M. D. Tapia, S. Kochhar, S. Black and G. Brighton Collaboration Small for Gestational Age Working, *Vaccine*, 2017, **35**, 6518-6528.
3. A. C. Lee, N. Kozuki, S. Cousens, G. A. Stevens, H. Blencowe, M. F. Silveira, A. Sania, H. E. Rosen, C. Schmiegelow, L. S. Adair, A. H. Baqui, F. C. Barros, Z. A. Bhutta, L. E. Caulfield, P. Christian, S. E. Clarke, W. Fawzi, R. Gonzalez, J. Humphrey, L. Huybregts, S. Kariuki, P. Kolsteren, J. Lusingu, D. Manandhar, A. Mongkolchat, L. C. Mullany, R. Ndyomugenyi, J. K. Nien, D. Roberfroid, N. Saville, D. J. Terlouw, J. M. Tielsch, C. G. Victora, S. C. Velaphi, D. Watson-Jones, B. A. Willey, M. Ezzati, J. E. Lawn, R. E. Black, J. Katz and C. S.-f.-G.-A.-P. B. W. Group, *BMJ*, 2017, **358**, j3677.
4. J. Katz, A. C. Lee, N. Kozuki, J. E. Lawn, S. Cousens, H. Blencowe, M. Ezzati, Z. A. Bhutta, T. Marchant, B. A. Willey, L. Adair, F. Barros, A. H. Baqui, P. Christian, W. Fawzi, R. Gonzalez, J. Humphrey, L. Huybregts, P. Kolsteren, A. Mongkolchat, L. C. Mullany, R. Ndyomugenyi, J. K. Nien, D. Osrin, D. Roberfroid, A. Sania, C. Schmiegelow, M. F. Silveira, J. Tielsch, A. Vaidya, S. C. Velaphi, C. G. Victora, D. Watson-Jones, R. E. Black and C. S.-f.-G.-A.-P. B. W. Group, *Lancet*, 2013, **382**, 417-425.
5. A. C. Lee, J. Katz, H. Blencowe, S. Cousens, N. Kozuki, J. P. Vogel, L. Adair, A. H. Baqui, Z. A. Bhutta, L. E. Caulfield, P. Christian, S. E. Clarke, M. Ezzati, W. Fawzi, R. Gonzalez, L. Huybregts, S. Kariuki, P. Kolsteren, J. Lusingu, T. Marchant, M. Merialdi, A. Mongkolchat, L. C. Mullany, J. Ndirangu, M. L. Newell, J. K. Nien, D. Osrin, D. Roberfroid, H. E. Rosen, A. Sania, M. F. Silveira, J. Tielsch, A. Vaidya, B. A. Willey, J. E. Lawn, R. E. Black and C. S.-P. B. W. Group, *Lancet Glob Health*, 2013, **1**, e26-36.
6. M. P. Wymann and R. Schneiter, *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*, 2008, **9**, 162-176.
7. X. Zhou, J. Mao, J. Ai, Y. Deng, M. R. Roth, C. Pound, J. Henegar, R. Welti and S. A. Bigler, *PLoS One*, 2012, **7**, e48889.
8. Z. Yu, H. Chen, J. Ai, Y. Zhu, Y. Li, J. A. Borgia, J. S. Yang, J. Zhang, B. Jiang, W. Gu and Y. Deng, *Oncotarget*, 2017, **8**, 107899-107906.
9. A. Sapandowski, M. Stope, K. Evert, M. Evert, U. Zimmermann, D. Peter, I. Page, M. Burchardt and L. Schild, *Mol Cell Biochem*, 2015, **410**, 175-185.
10. C. Stegemann, R. Pechlaner, P. Willeit, S. R. Langley, M. Mangino, U. Mayr, C. Menni, A. Moayyeri, P. Santer, G. Rungger, T. D. Spector, J. Willeit, S. Kiechl and M. Mayr, *Circulation*, 2014, **129**, 1821-1831.
11. G. B. Gugiu, *Methods Mol Biol*, 2017, **1609**, 65-82.

12. T. Cajka and O. Fiehn, *Trends Analyt Chem*, 2014, **61**, 192-206.
13. N. Sattar, A. Bendomir, C. Berry, J. Shepherd, I. A. Greer and C. J. Packard, *Obstet Gynecol*, 1997, **89**, 403-408.
14. S. M. Kim, S. M. Lee, S. J. Kim, B. J. Kim, S. Shin, J. R. Kim and K. H. Cho, *J Clin Lipidol*, 2017, **11**, 1318-1328 e1313.
15. B. Ghodke, R. Pusukuru and V. Mehta, *Cureus*, 2017, **9**, e1420.
16. C. D. Nayak, V. Agarwal and D. M. Nayak, *Indian J Clin Biochem*, 2013, **28**, 152-157.
17. J. N. Jones, C. Gercel-Taylor and D. D. Taylor, *Obstet Gynecol*, 1999, **93**, 527-531.
18. A. Arsic, V. Vucic, N. Prekajski, J. Tepsic, D. Ristic-Medic, V. Velickovic and M. Glibetic, *Hippokratia*, 2012, **16**, 230-235.
19. R. P. Horgan, D. I. Broadhurst, S. K. Walsh, W. B. Dunn, M. Brown, C. T. Roberts, R. A. North, L. M. McCowan, D. B. Kell, P. N. Baker and L. C. Kenny, *J Proteome Res*, 2011, **10**, 3660-3673.
20. M. S. Kramer, S. R. Kahn, M. Dahhou, J. Otvos, J. Genest, R. W. Platt and R. W. Evans, *J Pediatr*, 2013, **163**, 983-988.
21. A. C. Morillon, D. F. B. Leite, S. Yakkundi, L. A. Gethings, G. Thomas, P. N. Baker, L. C. Kenny, J. A. English and F. P. McCarthy, *Metabolomics*, 2021, **17**, 5.
22. T. Kiserud, A. Benachi, K. Hecher, R. G. Perez, J. Carvalho, G. Piaggio and L. D. Platt, *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, 2018, **218**, S619-S629.
23. A. H. Baqui, R. Khanam, M. S. Rahman, A. Ahmed, H. H. Rahman, M. I. Moin, S. Ahmed, F. Jehan, I. Nisar, A. Hussain, M. Ilyas, A. Hotwani, M. Sajid, S. Qureshi, A. Zaidi, S. Sazawal, S. M. Ali, S. Deb, M. H. Juma, U. Dhingra, A. Dutta, S. M. Ame, C. Hayward, I. Rudan, M. Zangenberg, D. Russell, S. Yoshida, O. Polasek, A. Manu and R. Bahl, *J Glob Health*, 2017, **7**, 021202.
24. J. Villar, L. Cheikh Ismail, C. G. Victora, E. O. Ohuma, E. Bertino, D. G. Altman, A. Lambert, A. T. Papageorgiou, M. Carvalho, Y. A. Jaffer, M. G. Gravett, M. Purwar, I. O. Frederick, A. J. Noble, R. Pang, F. C. Barros, C. Chumlea, Z. A. Bhutta, S. H. Kennedy, F. International and C. Newborn Growth Consortium for the 21st, *Lancet*, 2014, **384**, 857-868.
25. J. W. Lee, H. J. Mok, D. Y. Lee, S. C. Park, G. S. Kim, S. E. Lee, Y. S. Lee, K. P. Kim and H. D. Kim, *J Proteome Res*, 2017, **16**, 1460-1469.
26. C. J. Mitchell, M. S. Kim, C. H. Na and A. Pandey, *Mol Cell Proteomics*, 2016, **15**, 2829-2838.
27. M. M. Minter Baerg, S. D. Stoway, J. Hart, L. Mott, D. S. Peck, S. L. Nett, J. S. Eckerman, J. M. Lacey, C. T. Turgeon, D. Gavrilov, D. Oglesbee, K. Raymond, S. Tortorelli, D. Matern, L. Morkrid and P. Rinaldo, *Genet Med*, 2018, **20**, 847-854.
28. S. Tortorelli, J. S. Eckerman, J. J. Orsini, C. Stevens, J. Hart, P. L. Hall, J. J. Alexander, D. Gavrilov, D. Oglesbee, K. Raymond, D. Matern and P. Rinaldo, *Genet Med*, 2018, **20**, 840-846.
29. G. Marquardt, R. Currier, D. M. McHugh, D. Gavrilov, M. J. Magera, D. Matern, D. Oglesbee, K. Raymond, P. Rinaldo, E. H. Smith, S. Tortorelli, C. T. Turgeon, F. Lorey, B. Wilcken, V. Wiley, L. C. Greed, B. Lewis, F. Boemer, R. Schoos, S. Marie, M. F. Vincent, Y. C. Sica, M. T. Domingos, K.

- Al-Thihli, G. Sinclair, O. Y. Al-Dirbashi, P. Chakraborty, M. Dymerski, C. Porter, A. Manning, M. R. Seashore, J. Quesada, A. Reuben, P. Chrastina, P. Hornik, I. Atef Mandour, S. A. Atty Sharaf, O. Bodamer, B. Dy, J. Torres, R. Zori, D. Cheillan, C. Vianey-Saban, D. Ludvigson, A. Stembridge, J. Bonham, M. Downing, Y. Dotsikas, Y. L. Loukas, V. Papakonstantinou, G. S. Zacharioudakis, A. Barath, E. Karg, L. Franzson, J. J. Jonsson, N. N. Breen, B. G. Lesko, S. L. Berberich, K. Turner, M. Ruoppolo, E. Scolamiero, I. Antonozzi, C. Carducci, U. Caruso, M. Cassanello, G. la Marca, E. Pasquini, I. M. Di Gangi, G. Giordano, M. Camilot, F. Teofoli, S. M. Manos, C. K. Peterson, S. K. Mayfield Gibson, D. W. Sevier, S. Y. Lee, H. D. Park, I. Khneisser, P. Browning, F. Gulamali-Majid, M. S. Watson, R. B. Eaton, I. Sahai, C. Ruiz, R. Torres, M. A. Seeterlin, E. L. Stanley, A. Hietala, M. McCann, C. Campbell, P. V. Hopkins, M. G. de Sain-Van der Velden, B. Elvers, M. A. Morrissey, S. Sunny, D. Knoll, D. Webster, D. M. Frazier, J. D. McClure, D. E. Sesser, S. A. Willis, H. Rocha, L. Vilarinho, C. John, J. Lim, S. G. Caldwell, K. Tomashitis, D. E. Castineiras Ramos, J. A. Cocho de Juan, I. Rueda Fernandez, R. Yahyaoui Macias, J. M. Egea-Mellado, I. Gonzalez-Gallego, C. Delgado Pecellin, M. S. Garcia-Valdecasas Bermejo, Y. H. Chien, W. L. Hwu, T. Childs, C. D. McKeever, T. Tanyalcin, M. Abdulrahman, C. Queijo, A. Lemes, T. Davis, W. Hoffman, M. Baker and G. L. Hoffman, *Genet Med*, 2012, **14**, 648-655.
30. D. McHugh, C. A. Cameron, J. E. Abdenur, M. Abdulrahman, O. Adair, S. A. Al Nuaimi, H. Ahlman, J. J. Allen, I. Antonozzi, S. Archer, S. Au, C. Auray-Blais, M. Baker, F. Bamforth, K. Beckmann, G. B. Pino, S. L. Berberich, R. Binard, F. Boemer, J. Bonham, N. N. Breen, S. C. Bryant, M. Caggana, S. G. Caldwell, M. Camilot, C. Campbell, C. Carducci, S. C. Bryant, M. Caggana, S. G. Caldwell, M. Camilot, C. Campbell, C. Carducci, R. Cariappa, C. Carlisle, U. Caruso, M. Cassanello, A. M. Castilla, D. E. Ramos, P. Chakraborty, R. Chandrasekar, A. C. Ramos, D. Cheillan, Y. H. Chien, T. A. Childs, P. Chrastina, Y. C. Sica, J. A. de Juan, M. E. Colandre, V. C. Espinoza, G. Corso, R. Currier, D. Cyr, N. Czuczy, O. D'Apolito, T. Davis, M. G. de Sain-Van der Velden, C. Delgado Pecellin, I. M. Di Gangi, C. M. Di Stefano, Y. Dotsikas, M. Downing, S. M. Downs, B. Dy, M. Dymerski, I. Rueda, B. Elvers, R. Eaton, B. M. Eckerd, F. El Mougy, S. Eroh, M. Espada, C. Evans, S. Fawbush, K. F. Fijolek, L. Fisher, L. Franzson, D. M. Frazier, L. R. Garcia, M. S. Bermejo, D. Gavrilov, R. Gerace, G. Giordano, Y. G. Irazabal, L. C. Greed, R. Grier, E. Grycki, X. Gu, F. Gulamali-Majid, A. F. Hagar, L. Han, W. H. Hannon, C. Haslip, F. A. Hassan, M. He, A. Hietala, L. Himstedt, G. L. Hoffman, W. Hoffman, P. Hoggatt, P. V. Hopkins, D. M. Hougaard, K. Hughes, P. R. Hunt, W. L. Hwu, J. Hynes, I. Ibarra-Gonzalez, C. A. Ingham, M. Ivanova, W. B. Jacox, C. John, J. P. Johnson, J. J. Jonsson, E. Karg, D. Kasper, B. Klopfer, D. Katakouzinis, I. Khneisser, D. Knoll, H. Kobayashi, R. Koneski, V. Kozich, R. Kouapei, D. Kohlmuller, I. Kremensky, G. la Marca, M. Lavochnik, S. Y. Lee, D. C. Lehotay, A. Lemes, J. Lepage, B. Lesko, B. Lewis, C. Lim, S. Linard, M. Lindner, M. A. Lloyd-Puryear, F. Lorey, Y. L. Loukas, J. Luedtke, N. Maffitt, J. F. Magee, A. Manning, S. Manos, S. Marie, S. M. Hadachi,

- G. Marquardt, S. J. Martin, D. Matern, S. K. Mayfield Gibson, P. Mayne, T. D. McCallister, M. McCann, J. McClure, J. J. McGill, C. D. McKeever, B. McNeilly, M. A. Morrissey, P. Moutsatsou, E. A. Mulcahy, D. Nikoloudis, B. Norgaard-Pedersen, D. Oglesbee, M. Oltarzewski, D. Ombrone, J. Ojodu, V. Papakonstantinou, S. P. Reoyo, H. D. Park, M. Pasquali, E. Pasquini, P. Patel, K. A. Pass, C. Peterson, R. D. Pettersen, J. J. Pitt, S. Poh, A. Pollak, C. Porter, P. A. Poston, R. W. Price, C. Queijo, J. Quesada, E. Randell, E. Ranieri, K. Raymond, J. E. Reddic, A. Reuben, C. Ricciardi, P. Rinaldo, J. D. Rivera, A. Roberts, H. Rocha, G. Roche, C. R. Greenberg, J. M. Mellado, M. J. Juan-Fita, C. Ruiz, M. Ruoppolo, S. L. Rutledge, E. Ryu, C. Saban, I. Sahai, M. I. Garcia-Blanco, P. Santiago-Borrero, A. Schenone, R. Schoos, B. Schweitzer, P. Scott, M. R. Seashore, M. A. Seeterlin, D. E. Sesser, D. W. Sevier, S. M. Shone, G. Sinclair, V. A. Skrinska, E. L. Stanley, E. T. Strovel, A. L. Jones, S. Sunny, Z. Takats, T. Tanyalcin, F. Teofoli, J. R. Thompson, K. Tomashitis, M. T. Domingos, J. Torres, R. Torres, S. Tortorelli, S. Turi, K. Turner, N. Tzanakos, A. G. Valiente, H. Vallance, M. Vela-Amieva, L. Vilarinho, U. von Döbeln, M. F. Vincent, B. C. Vorster, M. S. Watson, D. Webster, S. Weiss, B. Wilcken, V. Wiley, S. K. Williams, S. A. Willis, M. Woontner, K. Wright, R. Yahyaoui, S. Yamaguchi, M. Yssel and W. M. Zakowicz, *Genet Med*, 2011, **13**, 230-254.
31. A. Tokumura, Y. Kanaya, M. Miyake, S. Yamano, M. Irahara and K. Fukuzawa, *Biol Reprod*, 2002, **67**, 1386-1392.
 32. S. Okudaira, H. Yukiura and J. Aoki, *Biochimie*, 2010, **92**, 698-706.
 33. K. D'Souza, G. V. Paramel and P. C. Kienesberger, *Nutrients*, 2018, **10**.
 34. X. Sheng, Y. C. Yung, A. Chen and J. Chun, *Development*, 2015, **142**, 1390-1395.
 35. T. Kobayashi, S. Yamano, S. Murayama, H. Ishikawa, A. Tokumura and T. Aono, *FEBS Lett*, 1994, **351**, 38-40.
 36. J. H. Hecht, J. A. Weiner, S. R. Post and J. Chun, *J Cell Biol*, 1996, **135**, 1071-1083.
 37. H. Sumida, K. Noguchi, Y. Kihara, M. Abe, K. Yanagida, F. Hamano, S. Sato, K. Tamaki, Y. Morishita, M. R. Kano, C. Iwata, K. Miyazono, K. Sakimura, T. Shimizu and S. Ishii, *Blood*, 2010, **116**, 5060-5070.
 38. X. Ye, M. K. Skinner, G. Kennedy and J. Chun, *Biol Reprod*, 2008, **79**, 328-336.
 39. M. Hack, N. Breslau, B. Weissman, D. Aram, N. Klein and E. Borawski, *N Engl J Med*, 1991, **325**, 231-237.
 40. H. M. de Bie, K. J. Oostrom and H. A. Delemarre-van de Waal, *Horm Res Paediatr*, 2010, **73**, 6-14.
 41. J. T. Brenna and G. Y. Diau, *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids*, 2007, **77**, 247-250.
 42. X. Wang, Y. Cui, X. Tong, H. Ye and S. Li, *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2007, **92**, 681-684.
 43. L. L. Lobo, H. U. Kumar, T. Mishra, T. Sundari, A. Singh, C. V. Kumar, G. K. Rao, B. Jahangir, V. Misale, P. Prashant, N. L. Gajiwala and A. S. Thakkar, *Indian J Med Res*, 2016, **144**, 194-199.

44. M. Serpytis, V. Karosas, R. Tamosauskas, J. Dementaviciene, K. Strupas, A. Sileikis and J. Sipylaite, *JOP*, 2012, **13**, 677-680.
45. M. R. Hentschke, C. E. Poli-de-Figueiredo, B. E. da Costa, L. O. Kurlak, P. J. Williams and H. D. Mistry, *J Lipid Res*, 2013, **54**, 2658-2664.
46. W. Mifsud and N. J. Sebire, *Fetal Diagn Ther*, 2014, **36**, 117-128.
47. M. Mizuuchi, T. Cindrova-Davies, M. Olovsson, D. S. Charnock-Jones, G. J. Burton and H. W. Yung, *J Pathol*, 2016, **238**, 550-561.
48. S. Longo, L. Bollani, L. Decembrino, A. Di Comite, M. Angelini and M. Stronati, *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med*, 2013, **26**, 222-225.

Tables

Table 1. Maternal and neonatal characteristics of small for gestational age (SGA) and appropriate for gestational age (AGA) babies in the AMANHI-Bangladesh pregnancy cohort and cohorts used in the study.

Maternal characteristics	All SGA cases* (N=511)	All AGA cases* (N=254)	SGA mothers** N=20	Control mothers** N=20
Maternal age, y				
≤19	127 (24.9%)	45 (17.7 %)	3 (15.0%)	2 (10.0%)
20-29	319 (62.4 %)	168 (66.2 %)	13 (65.0%)	14 (70.0%)
≥30	65 (12.7 %)	41 (16.1 %)	4 (20.0%)	4 (20.0%)
BMI ^a , kg/m ²				
<18.5	207 (40.5 %)	74 (29.1 %)	5 (25.0%)	0 (0%)
18.5-24.9	289 (56.6 %)	155 (61.0 %)	15 (75.0%)	15 (75.0%)
≥25.0	11 (2.1 %)	23 (9.1%)	0 (0%)	5 (25.0%)
% Primiparous	200 (39.1 %)	56 (22.1 %)	6 (30%)	3 (15%)
% Sniffs/chews tobacco	86 (16.8%)	41 (16.1 %)	4 (20%)	0 (0%)
% Sniffs/chews betelnut	191 (37.4 %)	98 (38.6 %)	9 (45%)	7 (35%)
Gestational age at delivery, days				
Mean (SD)	277.3 (11.8)	269.5 (17.2)	280.7 (8.1)	278 (9.6)
Median (IQR)	277 (13)	274 (20)	281.5 (13)	278 (11)
Gestational age at blood draw, days				
Mean (SD)	99.4 (22.1)	99.5 (23.0)	96.8 (19.8)	100.9 (22.4)
Median (IQR)	97 (37)	97 (39)	98.5 (23.5)	99.5 (32)
Wealth Quintile ^b				
Poorest	128 (25.1%)	42 (16.6 %)	4 (20%)	2 (10%)
Poor	104 (20.4 %)	44 (17.3 %)	5 (25%)	4 (20%)
Middle	107 (20.9 %)	58 (22.8 %)	6 (30%)	5 (25%)
Rich	111 (21.7 %)	62 (24.4 %)	4 (20%)	5 (25%)
Richest	60 (11.7 %)	48 (18.9 %)	1 (5%)	4 (20%)
% Used biomass for cooking	499 (97.6%)	242 (95.3 %)	19 (95%)	19 (95%)
Hemoglobin, g/dl				
8-19 weeks of gestation ^c				
Mean (SD)	11.2 (1.3)	11.3 (1.3)	11.2 (1.0)	11.1 (1.1)
Median (IQR)	11.3 (1.6)	11.4 (1.6)	11.5 (1.6)	11.0 (1.5)

Third trimester, 24-36 weeks of gestation ^d				
Mean (SD)	9.9 (1.3)	9.9 (1.3)	9.9 (1.1)	9.3 (1.1)
Median (IQR)	10.0 (1.6)	9.9 (1.4)	9.9 (0.9)	9.6 (2.1)
Blood Pressure at 24-28 weeks of gestation ^e				
Systolic BP: Median (IQR)	97 (13.0)	100 (13.0)	96 (13.5)	99 (12.0)
Diastolic BP: Median (IQR)	63 (10.0)	63 (10.0)	61 (10.5)	63.5 (9.0)
Normal BP (SBP<120 mm Hg and DBP<80 mm Hg)	478 (95.6%)	227 (93.0%)	18 (90.0%)	20 (100%)
Elevated BP (SBP120-129 mm Hg and DBP<80 mm Hg)	4 (0.8%)	5 (2.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Hypertension (SBP >=130 mm Hg or DBP >=80 mm Hg)	18 (3.6%)	12 (4.9%)	2 (10.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Neonatal characteristics				
% Male	233 (45.6 %)	129 (50.8 %)	9 (45.0 %)	12 (60 %)
Birth weight in gm				
Mean (SD)	2254.1 (290.2)	3294.9 (486.8)	2336.5 (161.8)	3435 (340.9)
Median (IQR)	2300 (370)	3390 (470)	2305 (215)	3400 (460)

Notes: No women in this cohort provided a history of smoking or alcohol consumption.

All numbers are n (%) unless otherwise specified.

*Abbreviations: AGA = appropriate for gestational age; BMI = body mass index; BP = blood pressure; DBP = diastolic blood pressure; IQR = interquartile range; SD = standard deviation; SBP = systolic blood pressure; SGA = small for gestational age.

*SGA: <3rd percentile; AGA:>50th percentile; **Cases: sample of SGA babies; Controls: sample of AGA babies

^a Data missing in mothers of 4 SGA and 2 AGA babies; ^b Data missing for 1 SGA baby; ^c Data missing for mothers of 3 SGA babies, 22 AGA babies, 4 cases and 2 controls; ^d Data missing for mothers of 67 SGA babies, 31 AGA babies, 4 cases and 2 controls; ^e Data missing for mothers of 11 SGA and 10 AGA babies.

Table 2. Ten informative lipid ratios used to construct single condition tool (Fig. 3C) to differentiate small for gestational (SGA) mothers from controls.

Lipid ratios	Overlap percentile between controls and SGA range (%)
d16:1/16:0-SM / 20:4-LPA	38.0
22:4-LPI / 20:4-LPA	40.3
14:0/16:0-PC / 20:4-LPA	45.2
18:2/24:0-DG / 20:4-LPA	45.4
d18:0/22:0-SM / 20:4-LPA	47.2
14:0e/16:0-PC / 18:1/18:2-PC	46.7
18:2e/16:1-DG / 48:1-TG	48.2
50:3e-TG / 54:1p-TG	41.8
20:2-ChE / 14:0e/18:1-PC	46.2
20:1e/20:3-dMePE / 50:3e-TG	48.4

*Abbreviations: ChE = cholesteryl ester; dMePE = dimethylphosphatidylethanolamine; DG = diglyceride; LPA = lysophosphatidic acid; LPI = lysophosphatidylinositol; PC = phosphatidylcholine; SGA = small for gestational age; TG = triglyceride.

Figure legends

Fig. 1. Overview of strategy for lipidomics analysis. Workflow for lipidomics analysis of maternal serum samples. After addition of internal standards to all samples, lipids were extracted from serum. By coupling reversed-phase liquid chromatography to high resolution mass spectrometry, global profiling of lipids was performed by switching positive and negative polarities throughout the run. We carried out qualitative confirmation, followed by quantitative measurement of serum lipids. Serum lipids that are expressed differentially in SGA were discovered using statistical analysis.

Fig. 2. Base peak chromatograms and MS/MS spectra using LC-MS/MS. (A) MS/MS spectra of 16:0/22:4-PI at 15.2 min and 18:0/20:4-PI at 15.5 min detected by LC-MS/MS. Fragments ions in red confirm distinguished identities of PI isomers. (B) MS/MS spectra of 52:3-TG. Fragments ions confirm simultaneous elution of multiple TG isomers. Fragment ion in red confirm various acyl chain combinations of 52:3-TG.

Fig. 3. Alterations of maternal serum lipids. (A) X-axis represents relative fold-changes (SGA/controls) as indicated with Y-axis depicting the statistical significance (P -value). Each circle represents lipid species analyzed in the study. The points in red indicate lysophosphatidic acid that were analyzed in the study. 20:4-lysophosphatidic that was significantly increased ($P=.05$) in mothers who delivered SGA neonates is indicated. (B) Triglyceride species analyzed in the study are shown in red. (C) Collaborative Laboratory Integrated Reports (CLIR) dual scatter plot applied for differentiating SGA cases from controls. Each plot is divided in four quadrants by orthogonal lines drawn at the midpoint between the lowest combined score of one condition and the highest one of the other condition as indicated: Lower right quadrant: consistent with SGA (orange circles); Upper right: indeterminate (both conditions are possible); Upper left: consistent with controls

(orange circles); Lower left: neither condition. The SGA case with the score of the single condition tool for SGA closest to the 50th percentile rank, 56th percentile, (N=10) is indicated with an arrow. Min-max score indicates a normalization algorithm to keep all scores within 0 and 100. Each result is calculated by subtracting from the score the lowest of all scores, dividing it by the range of values (highest minus lowest), and multiplying it by 100. This formula preserves the relative distance between values and is ideal to achieve consistency among tools comparing any two conditions.

Fig. 4. Bar graphs of serum lipids altered in SGA mothers. Relative peak area of species from (A) lysophosphatidic acid, (B) triglyceride species between mothers who delivered appropriate for gestational age and SGA neonates are shown with error bars.

Fig. 5. Changes in lysophosphatidic acid in SGA mothers. (A) Abundance of total and individual subspecies of lysophosphatidic acid in SGA mothers are shown in bar graphs (error bars indicate standard error of the mean of total LPA). While total LPA was decreased in SGA mothers by 33% ($P=.08$), 20:4-LPA was decreased by 32% ($P=.05$). 18:2-LPA by 44% ($P=.18$), 18:0-LPA by 37% ($P=.18$), 16:0-LPA by 32% ($P=.24$) and 18:1-LPA by 6% ($P=.54$). Student's t-test was used to calculate P -value. Each colored box represents abundance of individual lysophosphatidic acid containing the indicated fatty acyl chains. The structure of lysophosphatidic is shown on the right (fatty acyl chains indicated in red). (B) Association of lysophosphatidic acid level alterations with SGA neonates is illustrated. Elevated levels are indicated as red arrows and decreased levels are indicated as green arrows. Elevation of lysophospholipase D increases production of lysophosphatidic acid from lysophospholipids, which contributes to normal fetal development. Decreased activity of lysophospholipase D decreases production of lysophosphatidic acid, which can contribute to birth of SGA neonates. Increased triglycerides also contribute to appropriate for

age neonates. Decreased activity of lysophospholipase D decreases production of lysophosphatidic acid, which can contribute to the birth of small for gestational age neonates.

Figure 1

Figure 2

A

B

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 4

